

Acoustic prediction and testing for “Basajaun” EU Project demo building using neural network, prediction for innovative wooden partition wall with composites and bio-based insulation

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ABSTRACT

“Basajaun” is a major European innovation action about sustainable building with wood. The main objective is to demonstrate how wood construction chains can be optimized to foster both rural development and urban transformation whilst being connected with sustainable forest management in Europe. The project scrolls the full value chain of wood construction in Europe, and it include a demo project in south of France demonstrating implementation of various innovations, among which the studied innovative facade made of pultruded composites, structural insulated panels (SIP) plywood, wooden cladding and bio-based insulation. In building projects, partition walls are commonly designed for mechanical stability, thermal insulation and fire safety, in this article authors focus on acoustic aspects starting from design, optimization, lab testing, implementation specifications and in situ validation. For the design and optimization phase, authors developed prediction tool based on Artificial Intelligence. Programming and data feeding of the tool is described, and predictions are compared to laboratory measurements.

1. INTRODUCTION

Acoustics design comes in the early stages, along with the structural stability, dimensional stability, thermal insulation and fire resistance. One way to fight effectively noise transmission is to value

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experience, knowhow and use modeling tools in order to develop effective solutions that meet the regulations.

For Basajaun project, two demo buildings are studied. To comply with acoustic regulations the focus is given on the design of the partition walls the facades and the roof. First, we start with the acoustic regulation in Finland and in France, where demonstrators are planned to be constructed. Then, we will give some advice for the design of structural junctions that can affect acoustics for impact and airborne noise. And finally, we will exploit some test results of similar buildups to predict acoustic performances of Basajaun innovative materials and innovative building systems.

Building noise can be classified into two broad categories

- airborne noise, such as outdoor noise, traffic, urban agitation, as well as interior noise: television, radio, musical instruments, speech, etc.
- structure-borne noise, such as footsteps or equipment noises e.g. elevators, heating, etc.

2. ACOUSTIC DESIGN

2.1 Acoustic regulation

Figure 1 : French acoustic regulation, Outdoor traffic noise insulation $D_{n,T,A,tr} = 30$ dB (facades); Airborne noise insulation $D_{n,T,A} \geq 53$ to 58 dB (separative wall) and Standardized impact noise level $L'_{nT,w} \leq 58$ dB (between dwellings).

Finnish acoustic regulation: Outdoor traffic noise insulation $R'_{w+Ctr} = 30$ dB (facades); Airborne noise insulation $D_{nT,w} \geq 55$ dB (separative wall) and Standardized impact noise level $L'_{nT,w} + C_{150} \leq 53$ dB (between dwellings).

The French demo building is placed in a quiet area, so the requirement for airborne insulation against outdoor noise is the minimum value $D_{n,T,A,tr} = 30$ dB, for facades and roofs.

2.2 Artificial neural networks model ANN

The database of the ANN model developed includes 111 standardized laboratory measurements obtained from Lund University in Sweden, The National Research Council (NRC-CNRC) [1] in Canada and FCBA Institut Technologique in France. The measurements consist of airborne insulation measurements of 111 different walls in one-third-octave bands ranging from 50 Hz to 5 kHz. These measurements were conducted according to ISO 10140-2 (2010) [2] and ASTM E90- 09 (2016) [3]. The measurements performed in compliance with ASTM standards have been converted to the ISO 717-1 (2013) [4] descriptor (the weighted airborne sound R_w) in order to have a consistent agreement between insulation data. This conversion is necessary to standardize the acoustic descriptors in the

measurements. Various parameters are used to train the network model, and are chosen based on the type of façade component, their installation position, thickness and density of each layer, depth of studs and spacing between them, area of a façade (S), volume of a receiving room (V), group and total thickness and mass of a structure, resilient metal channel depth and spacing between them (see Table 1). The output/target of the ANN model is the value of airborne sound reduction index in one-third-octave bands. Despite the significant effect of certain elastic properties on the sound transmission, such as dynamic stiffeners and the modulus of elasticity of each material, they are not taken into account in the input parameters due to the lack of information in acoustic measurement reports.

Table 1: Structural parameters that are used as input parameters for ANN model

Parameter	Unit	Class
Material type	-	i.e., Insulation layer, gypsumboard, etc.
Material installation order	-	first, second, etc.
Material thickness	mm	-
Total thickness of wall	mm	-
Material density	kg/m ³	-
Total density	kg/m ³	-
Wall area S	m ²	-
Volume of receiving room V	m ³	-
Stud depth	mm	-
Spacing between studs	mm	-
Resilient channels depth	mm	-
Spacing between resilient channels depth	mm	-

For ANN model, a multilayer perceptron class of ANN with two hidden layers is used, each layer containing 40 and 30 artificial neurons, respectively. Crossvalidation technique is employed to validate the network model and prevent overfitting issues [5, 6]. LeakyReLU is chosen as the activation function for the hidden layers in order to avoid the vanishing gradient problem that could face other activation functions, such as tan or sigmoid [7]. For training, the Adam optimizer is used to minimize the errors of the prediction model [8, 9, 10]. 80% of the total number of measurements are allocated to the training set, 10% to the validation set and 10% to the testing set. The training set is used to develop the network parameters, such as bias and weights. The validation set is used to optimize the hyperparameters of the model, such as the number of hidden layers and neurons. Since the predictions are continuous values (insulation curves), the root mean-square error (RMSE) function can be used as a cost function to evaluate the predictive capability [11, 12].

3. PARTITIONS

For partition acoustic design, we give some advices about details that can affect acoustics for impact and airborne noise. And we propose some test results and prediction for acoustic performances of Basajaun innovative materials.

3.1 Acoustic regulation in Finland and in France

For dwelling separative walls the requirement for airborne insulation is

- $D_{n,T,A} \geq 53$ dB, in France and
- $D_{n,T,A} \geq 55$ dB, in Finland

3.2 Wall description and implementation recommendations

To achieve significant results with constructions made wood-based materials, the following points must be observed:

- use panels with a high surface mass, from 10 to 15 kg / m²;
- double the panel on each surface of the wall: with two layers of panels, the surface mass is doubled while keeping the same rigidity, the critical frequency remains unchanged and the doubling of mass provides additional insulation;
- ensure a minimum cavity of 60 mm between the panels;
- absorption in cavity by filling the space between panels with mineral wool;
- fix the walls as loosely as possible to the common structure, on an ad hoc basis, it is necessary to avoid at most the rigid connections between the two facings via the framework;
- prefer a double or alternating frame, the panels will be fixed in a uncoupled way.
- no continuity in junctions.
- no contact between the two structures,
- no holes are permitted, no electric boxes,
- Separative wall should be continuous from ground floor to roof,

3.3 South demo design and optimization of separative walls

First building system for partition proposed was composed of 2 SIP panels of 100 mm plus one plasterboard and one plywood on wooden studs on both sides, see the picture below:

	R _w [dB]	C ₁₀₀₋₃₅₀₀ [dB]	C ₅₀₋₅₀₀₀ [dB]
Measured values	54	-6	-8
Predicted ANN values	53	-4	-4

This first calculation ends up with a low acoustic performance. This construction will not allow us to reach the minimum sound insulation requirements for both France and Finland regulations. For improvement, there are few options:

- the inner plywood boards have to be perforated in order to become acoustically transparent. It is also possible to remove them as they have no structural role.
- try to have the pipes inside the wall instead of having an extra cavity on each side. We can increase the thickness of the insulation instead.

1st proposal for acoustic separative wall:

Airborne sound insulation

	R_w / D_{nTw} [dB]	$C_{100-3500}$ [dB]	$C_{50-5000}$ [dB]
Measured values	64	-3	-6
Predicted ANN values	66	-1	-2

2nd proposal for acoustic separative wall:

The second proposal, can be considered in case of cavity is needed for pipes, A bit less good for acoustics, estimation attached as well.

Airborne sound insulation

	R_w [dB]	$C_{100-3500}$ [dB]	$C_{50-5000}$ [dB]
Measured values	71	-7	-14
Predicted ANN values	75	-10	-13

3rd proposal for acoustic separative wall:
Calculated airborne sound insulation

	R_w [dB]	$C_{100-3500}$ [dB]	$C_{50-5000}$ [dB]
Measured values	66	-2	-9
Predicted ANN values	64	-5	-5

Final solution

	R_w [dB]	$C_{100-3500}$ [dB]	$C_{50-5000}$ [dB]
Predicted ANN values	73	-6	-9

5. COMMENTS AND CONCLUSIONS

ANN perform good predictions with a good confident domain. In early articles Bader Eddin [11] and [12] could evaluate the predictive capability on wooden walls, wooden facades and wooden floors. Concerning proposals 1, 2 and 3, ANN calculation can be used with a good confident domain.

The final solution will be implemented by “Bouygues Construction” on the French Demo building in the “Collège Du Pian Medoc” owned by “Département de Gironde”. Before the implementation the wall will be tested, in Tecnia’s acoustic facility in June 2023. And finally the wall will be tested in-situ in September 2023.

Timber structured separative walls can perform high insulation levels. But it is also subject to flanking transmissions due to vibro-acoustic transmissions through junctions. Designers know that flanking transmissions will decrease insulation by 3 to 8 dB. Thus, they adapt walls and floors to that matter. Another way of predicting flanking transmission is to use calculation models using Statistical Energy Analysis (SEA).

In previous articles Authors presented some measures of vibration reduction indices for wooden buildings as well as calculation strategies using SEA and in-situ measurements [13]. Derived from SEA, simplified models have been elaborated for monolithic concrete walls forming a ‘T’ or a cross junction: EN 12354 [14].

With measured junctions and experts’ knowledge-based approach authors were able to design the building structures and details of structural junctions of the French demo building. Specifically, junction detail drawings to be used in between the dwellings.

The partition walls must be continuous from the ground floor to the roof. And special attention is given to the structural connection between the partition and the first level floor. The loading structure is composed of poles and beams that will be hidden in the partition walls. The structure, in the separative zone, is preferably double, disconnected, and each dwelling is loaded by his own structure.

The work presented in this article is the result of several years of acoustic cooperation between Authors [15, 16] starting from the COST action FP0702: “Net-Acoustics for Timber based Lightweight Buildings and Elements” (2008-2012). Then the "Silent Timber Build" project (2013-2017) on innovative prediction tools for timber structures. Theories used in prediction models were based on Finite element simulations (FEM), on Statistical Energy Analysis (SEA) and on hybrid approaches to predict acoustical behavior of light weight timber constructions.

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REFERENCES

1. Halliwell, R. E.; Nightingale, T. R. T.; Warnock, A. C. C.; Birta, J. A., Gypsum board walls: transmission loss data; Institute for Research in Construction, National Research Council Canada: Ottawa, ON, Canada, 1998. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4224/20331556>.
2. ISO.140-2; Acoustics—Laboratory Measurement of Sound Insulation of Building Elements—Part 2: Measurement of Airborne Sound Insulation. International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2010.
3. ASTM.E90-09; Standard Test Method for Laboratory Measurement of Airborne Sound Transmission Loss of Building Partitions and Elements. ASTM International: West Conshohocken, PA, USA, 2016.
4. ISO.717-1; Acoustics—Rating of Sound Insulation in Buildings and of Buildings Elements—Part 1: Airborne Sound Insulation. International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2013.
5. Nielsen, M.A. Neural Networks and Deep Learning; Determination Press: San Francisco, CA, USA, 2015. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4249/scholarpedia.32832>.
6. Géron, A. Hands-on Machine Learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow: Concepts, Tools, and Techniques to Build Intelligent Systems; O'Reilly Media, Inc.: Newton, MA, USA, 2019.
7. Xu, J.; Li, Z.; Du, B.; Zhang, M.; Liu, J. Reluplex made more practical: Leaky ReLU. In Proceedings of the 2020 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC), Rennes, France, 7–10 July 2020; IEEE: Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCC50000.2020.9219587>.
8. Ruder, S. An overview of gradient descent optimization algorithms. arXiv 2016, arXiv:1609.04747. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1609.04747>.
9. Kingma D.P, Ba J. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. arXiv 2014, arXiv:1412.6980. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1412.6980>.
10. Tato, A.; Nkambou, R. Improving adam optimizer. 2018. Accessed on: 2021 November 09.
11. Bader Eddin M, Ménard S, Bard Hagberg D, Kouyoumji J-L, Vardaxis, N.-G. Prediction of Sound Insulation Using Artificial Neural Networks—Part I: Lightweight Wooden Floor Structures. *Acoustics* 2022, 4, 203–226. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/acoustics4010013>
12. Bader Eddin M, Vardaxis NG, Ménard S, Bard Hagberg D, Kouyoumji J-L. Prediction of Sound Insulation Using Artificial Neural Networks—Part II: Lightweight Wooden Façade Structures. *Applied Sciences*. 2022 Jul 10; 12(14):6983. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12146983>.
13. Kouyoumji Jean-Luc, Fuente Marta, Measurement and prediction of flanking transmissions in wooden CLT constructions using Reverse-SEA, *Internoise 2018 proceedings*, 26-30 August 2018, Chicago.
14. EN.12354; Building Acoustics—Estimation of Acoustic Performance of Buildings from the Performance of Elements—Part 1: Airborne Sound Insulation between Rooms. International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2017.
15. Bard Delphine, Borello Gerard, Guigou Catherine and Kouyoumji Jean-Luc Challenges for acoustic calculation models in "silent timber build" The 21st ICSV International Congress on Sound and Vibration, 13-17 July, 2014, Beijing/China
16. Bard, Delphine, Negreira, Juan, Kouyoumji, Jean-Luc, Borello, Gérard, Guigou, Catherine, Challenges for acoustic calculation models in "Silent Timber Build", Part 1- FEM *Internoise 2014*, 16-19 November, Melbourne Australia,